

THE SMOLDERING ISSUES OF LABOURERS PROBLEMS IN THE MIDST OF COVID-19 CATASTROPHE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

With the impact of the tears and fears of COVID-19 lockdown in India, to be affected by the activity of income generation of poor sections of our society. Now we are all escaping from viral attack, on the other hand, our Indian labourers look at a job sudden destruction and face the numerous numbers of challenges at the present and future scenario for their livelihood's opportunity. Livelihoods are nowadays severe opposition between the states. To over this unemployment crisis, relief measures are the speedy manner in the form of regular employment to all sections of the labourers after the wind up to the lockdown in India.

This paper mainly concentrates on the pros, and cons of lockdown in India, as the consequences of the entire section of our labour forces live with us.

Keywords: *Infant Industries, Domestic Agriculture, Infrastructure Investment, Budgetary Allocation, Extreme poverty.*

INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented twenty-one days of the lockdown in India is seriously affecting the working Classes of people in India. Millions of Indians WHO rely on every day's wages for their everyday meal were now thrown out of their jobs. They are being afraid of livelihood opportunities only. They are thinking about "What Next? If our lives are an identical condition, our earning power will be tough in the next few days or if we alleviate the following twenty-one days we will face the mental health aspect with regard to financial as well as the family burden in the future time, even though they will get proper wages and also they are afraid of availability of work are shrinking together after the twenty-one days lockdown in India.

As a consequence, the countries' demand the goods and services are highly correlated with entire sections of labourers in India. If the demand is lower, its reflection enters into overall Economic growth falls into the less than 2 percent. Hence, this outcome of Economic growth is really challenging for the next 5 to 10 years or simply more than one decade.

This paper mainly highlighted the burning issues of labourers in India by the serious attack of COVID-19.

Firstly, the Migrant workers are violated by Rules and Regulations of lockdown situation in India

It is a strong complaint from all Sections of our society. It is true, even though, our central and state governments do not take adequate steps to how to send the workers their own place of origin and as transport alternatives dried up, many families in New Delhi and other large cities simply started to walk to their distant villages, with very little access to food. Basically, the large of buses, trains and other private transport facilities available, whereas properly coordinated not in time, definitely, it is a serious loophole before in the implementation of lockdown act. In general, because they are all illiterate peoples and they have a worried mentality because they come from extreme poverty basin. On the other hand, the labourers are one of the main stimuli of the whole Economy. If we ignore the wants of the labour class, we will face difficulty in the field of the Economic development Index at the World Level.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The present study mainly focuses on the subsequent objectives.

- 1. To assess the impact on the various labour classes with the sudden invent of lockdown in India.**
- 2. To find out the multifaceted problems affected the unorganized labourers in India.**
- 3. To analyze the financial burden of the unorganized labourers in India.**
- 4. To Study the creation of employment opportunities by way of government schemes.**
- 5. As a policymaker view on the strengthens of the Economic position of informal workers in India.**

METHODOLOGY:

This article based on the events occurred by the COVID-19 especially day to day life of the labourers, Migrant workers, Agricultural workers and casual labourers. It is based upon the same of the observations with the report to the labour Economics scenario after that arriving at the production of this article by authors (or) researchers. The author's motivation explores the present effect of the employment position. In this article provide the suggestions and policy recommendations to improve the livelihood condition of labour class in India. This Article only focused (or) covered on Labour Issue.

1.HINDRANCE IN THE LABOUR ECONOMY

The 21 days of lockdown against the COVID-19, without precaution any measures than the govt reinforce the order is really indelible scar in the history of both rural and urban labour masses in India. The majority of the labourers are walking more than 1000 Kilometers when the labourers touch upon their home places. The informal sector workers are Daily wage laboueres, Electricians, plumbers, Domestic workers, Hotel labouerers , Ragpickers, manual scavengers, home base government workers, beedi workers, Street vendors, Tea pickers, Rickshaw pullers,

Auto drivers, Tourism workers, Construction workers, Railway porters, and Real estate workers are facing the alarming situation of lack of employment opportunities for the livelihood of day to day life circle.

As the consequence, the informal labourers purchasing power will diminish beyond the limit, when compared to the average necessity of life, In practical, in an Economy supply is more, demand is less, the Market glut is taken place. Therefore, Market glut would lead to shut down in the Industrial sector.

Moreover, most of the workers are fear that dying of Hunger and uncertain for the employment opportunity. Thus Lockdown even would hamper the labour Economics scenario in India.

2. THE MYRIAD PROBLEMS FACED BY INFORMAL LABOURERS

In India's lockdown, due to COVID-19, the following problems faced by unorganized labourers as well as migrant labourers riddled with the issues like non-availability of work, the disparity of wages, if he or she comes in the place of destination after the end of lockdown, low-paid wages in the place of origin, hazardous nature of work, the sexual exploitation of women and children they belong to migrant labourer families, denial of state services such as health and education. Moreover, there are large mental health issues, then the non- acceptance of relatives and friends of migrant labourers hometown. The paucity of fund constraints does not solve the dark side of dept as well as poverty-ridden and so on. The most informal migrant workers are not easy to obtain the ration cards, Voter ID and Aadhaar card. These are all necessary documents, which is useful for getting sort welfare schemes with speedy manner.

For instance, if a migrant worker enters into their hometown (or) native villages, the general public of the people concern village, do not recognize the one and all of the village, they are thinking about diseases if Migrant labourers are enter into the village . Therefore, we ignore (or) cancel his relationship (or) friendship.

In this kind of environment, definitely would affect the real life of Migrant workers.

3.TO RECTIFY THE FINANCIAL BURDEN OF INFORMAL WORKERS WOULD AMPLIFY THE BETTER FUTURE.

The continuous shut down would lead to losses of 45 working days for their present employment level, As of now there is no cash on hand for their basic necessity of life, on the other hand, there is no let-up to meet the future expenses. The majority of the informal sector's labourers are getting money from professional money lenders in the name of weekly Thandal (Thandal means a collection of money Kanduvatti) even it was happening in normal working days, in the routine thandal money transaction, many of the labourers do not promptly pay the weekly Thandal , because of the sudden rise of some kind of family expenditure.

Whereas, in the midst of lockdown, their financial burden is surmounted, either live or not in the coming days. The Informal sector's labourers contribution to our economy is of grave importance. Therefore, the government should initiate a possible solution to overcome the problem of a financial burden.

4.EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES IT IS A BOON TO THE INFORMAL WORKERS.

To strengthen and create employment opportunities by way of government's continuous effort for the betterment of life of Informal Workers. All informal workers should cover Rent-Free shelters. The government should implement the special provident fund scheme say, for example, if one informal labourer, he can pay Rs.100, then the govt would pay Rs.1,000, this 10 fold share by the authorities, would alleviate poverty and create self - employment opportunity in future. The free medical facilities provided by the government as well as private hospitals, it will use to better health status of Informal worker.

If it improves the good health of informal workers, it should enlarge the working capacity of the informal labourers. To Provide adequate employment opportunities, through this way, if any one person gave the informal workers identity card, the government and private sectors provide the minimum no of days of employment per month (or) per year. To increase the involvement of

working tendency of informal workers, the government should allow the scheme of the subsidized rate of transport facility, during the working days.

In order to secure more no of employment opportunities, the government must enact the law for the development of domestic Agriculture and infant Industries in the remote areas.

Finally, the government should spontaneously invest in infrastructure development, it will create more no of employment opportunities in the large section of our informal sector labourers in India.

5.THE RIGHT POLICY DECISION WOULD PROMOTE THE INFORMAL LABOUR ECONOMY

The policymaker's attention toward the improvement of the economic status of Informal Workers in India. In this regard, the international Labours organization warns Indian Administrators and policymakers of our Nation. The ILO states that 90 per cent of the labour force (Nearly 40 Crore People) belongs to the informal category of workers in India, their living condition of the present day scenario of lockdown is worsening and falling risk of extreme poverty when compared to normal working days.

In order to overcome this problem, the labour sector reforms to introduce by the policymakers of India.

The reform measures are as follows

- Decent wage level and pension scheme for old-age workers.
- Labour welfare services such as health education, Nutrition.
- Special pay and included with the avail of leave facility for Extra working hours
- Union as well as state government insurance schemes
- Commensurate infrastructure development both in rural and urban areas
- Special budgetary Allocation to the informal Sector Workers.

The above all these viable and reliable policy measures to uplift the life of Informal workers in India, against the COVID-19 event.

CASE STUDIES WITH REGARD TO LOCK DOWN- MYRIAD PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY WORKERS IN THE INFORMAL SECTOR:

In this case study, we carefully study the myriad difficulties handled by migrant workers in the informal sector. The government's sudden announcement of 21-day COVID -19 lockdown has already disproportionately hurt marginalized communities due to loss of livelihood and lack of food, shelter, health, and other basic needs more than 80 percent of out-of-work migrant workers are stranded, with rail and bus services shut down.

The complete closing of state boundaries has hampered the supply of important goods, that leading to fears of price increases and scarcity. Thousands of homeless people need protection, more than 80 percent of India's workers are working in the informal sector One-third are ordinary labourers. It is important that authorities use the maximum resources available to ensure the delivery of services.

Migrant workers faced discrimination from their Villagers, neighbors and landlords threatened to evict them, fearing they could be carriers of COVID-19. Isolated people are also tarnished and threatened with expulsion. This real sadness at social discrimination against migrant workers.

Already, the serious consequences of the lockdown in have not been documented by the contracts and protections of millions of informal workers and daily wage workers across India and facing destitution and hunger.

All these informal workers are already food insecure, and they depend on daily wages for their living expenses, and provide vital health care, and educate their kids. Control will have a very genuine cost in contractual conditions of lives. Virus Lockdowns Threaten Billions of Informal workers working in the Shadow Economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

In the present, research work is entitled to COVID -19 lockdown and how the informal sector worker's daily lives affecting the sudden destruction and encounter the numerous numbers of challenges at the present and future scenario for their livelihoods. The studies on informal workers with reference to labourers in India. The connected review of literature of this analysis work highlights solely on informal sector worker's acts at varying levels. At this backdrop, the present research work carried out in the vacuum of many of the earlier studies.

CASE STUDY NO: 1

COVID-19 Lockdown – Fisherman's Normal Life Becomes Cessation

Guest workers are in trouble without wages at Kanyakumari harbor. The migrant Guest workers from Odisha, West Bengal and Assam are facing the insecure position of their livelihood. The Times of India reporter was approached by Radha Das, 48 from a village near Kolkata and his brother Nandu Das, 40 With the request of Some food.

They are basically unable to communicate in the local language and they tried to speak in Hindi. “Our employer is from Kollam, in Kerala. He dropped us here and left. During the past ten days without the money, we survive on scraps of the crew on another boat” said Radha Das

The Migrant workers are really employed on the deep-sea fishing boats in Kanyakumari, Thoothoor Region. With business at a standstill, the boats no longer have adequate provision to maintain them, at the same time groceries are going dry for several, others are about to run out of cooking gas, add to this the rules of lockdown. “We do not have masks so I was pursued by the police as soon as I tried to leave the harbour, we need help,” said Radha Das from Kolkata, who's been working as a fisherman for last five years.

Thus, boat owners do not have any responsibility to overcome the migrant guest worker's basic issues.

CASE STUDY NO:2***COVID-19 Lockdown Creates Mental and Physical Anguish for Migrant Workers***

Migrant workers cut off the plaster, starts limping his way home, 240Km away: A shocking incident happened at the Indore, Madhya Pradesh. A Migrant worker Bhawarlal cut off the plaster from his fractured leg and began hobbling his way from Indore to Rajasthan on March 30, 2020, during the lockdown in India due to coronavirus impact. He has over 240 Kilometers of agony left before he will get to his village in Rajasthan photos of him sitting on the road and removing his plaster cast went Viral in the morning, mirroring the plight of the thousands of migrant workers headed both ways, while the mass is returning to Madhya Pradesh from neighboring states. Bhawarlal is going from pipariya in Madhya Pradesh Hoshangabad district to baran in mandsaor district of Madhya Pradesh on March 30, 2020, and told that only pedestrians would be allowed any further, say sources from Indore.

Therefore, it is an inhuman act, at the lockdown against the Migrant Worker in India.

CASE STUDY NO:3***Epidemic Lockdown Transformed Agriculture Workers: Scared to go to work:***

In Samastipur District Farmer Mr. Manuwant Chowdhary, who cultivates the grain, vegetables, fruits and raises livestock on his farm, was informed that the workers he employed local residents who lived directly across the road. However, they were refusing to come to work.

They are afraid of even crossing the road and going to the farm because they think they will not be allowed to return, there are so much stigmatization and propaganda now about the virus that the villagers have stopped getting out entirely. When I informed one of my manual workers that she would be washing her hands regularly, and we won't be able to even farm while keeping the social distance within the field.

Coronavirus epidemic might cripple India's economy, India's epidemic lockdown is transformed into a human disaster More than half of India's labour force is taking part in farming, while agriculture contributes. India is one of the world's largest producers of crops such as rice, grains, sugar-cane, yarn, vegetables, and dairy products. Present there are concerns that halting farm activities in the field will not only end ups harming the farmers, and labourers but also have an impact on food security. This lockdown couldn't have arrived at the worst possible time for Migrant and Non-Migrant labourers.

REVIEW-1

Pavan K. Verma in his article on “India versus Bharat” describes the Indian middle-class people as a special case of the animal. Lockdown has strengthened India against the Bharat split. For those living in India, self-isolation is not always worrying, but enduring.

This is almost a fascinating opportunity for the facilitators. Doing yoga, drinking watermelon juice, watching Netflix, videoconferencing, reading books you haven't read yet, spending quality time with family, playing with pets, and being respectful to everyone about the importance of staying at home. But in India, millions of migrant workers are in the informal sector, street vendors, contract workers, lower-level employees at workplaces that have been shut down, and the daily wage laborers have to go out and work for something to eat at night.

India, aware of the imperatives of Bharat's deniers who have virtually no social security nets, is self-interested in isolation? Does the great Indian middle class know that India has the right to a less privileged one? It wants to get it back outside the castle, and thousands are stuck on the road Can't get back to their own place without work?

Thus, we have to identify both extremes of Versus Bharat of India.

REVIEW-2

Gurcharan Das in his article focused the Ten steps to \$5 Trillion. He brings out India must execute bold economic reforms to become competitive among the global level, out of which, the

sixth measure is labour reforms, as the consequence we can move forward to \$5 Trillion dollars. The sixth reform is mainly identified as the majority of the Indian labour laws that protect jobs not workers. It is revealed that the absence of labour wellbeing, the employers really can motivate the sucked out the hard work of their labourers blood, companies have to survive. On the downside when orders fall, you cut workers or go bankrupt. Successful Countries allow employers to hire and remove employees but protect the out of work with the safety net. There should be labour welfare funds in India (With the participation of employers and the government) to fund interim unemployment and re-training. We should not emphasize on lifetime jobs.

REVIEW-3

Ajeet Mahale , Jatin Anand, and Omar Rashid, their combined article on The long march to uncertainty reveals the migrant workers struggle in packet shelters, while those who managed to reach their native places face hostility. According to the 2011 census, the country has the highest number of immigrants There are (2.3 million) in Maharashtra but activists say the census failed to address the seasonal migration of four to five months.

For 20-year-old Digambar Roy, last week was a nightmare. He arrived in Mumbai from Jharkhand on March 21, hoping to earn a few months before returning home He knew nothing about lockdown; He was told he could earn as much as? 400 a day as a construction worker I don't have money to spend because after reaching the location lockdown started no work. I'm having difficulty getting rations. I rely on other workers from Jharkhand to help me.” he said.

According to Raghav Mehrotra, a researcher with the Ajvika Bureau, which works with migrant workers. What is now connecting all the migrant workers in the area is that they have all lost their jobs and wages, the Migrant worker's communities where all work, normally work in small cloths workshops. They stay at their place of work and rely on local tapas for their daily meals They were able to get basic rations by transferring money to their nearest grocery store, although cooking the meal It was a challenging task, he said, with many migrant workers gathering and asking for help.

Manas Raut from Odisha residing in a Rafale and works on the suburb of the city Routh said that he and 70 workers from his state were given help after a distress call was sent out on the Internet. Many have established their own helpline numbers "None of our employers have contacted us. We are fighting to fill both ends during this lockdown." he said.

The lockdown also exposed the absence of a protection net for migrant workers for example, many construction workers were found to be ineligible for finance in accordance with the building and other construction workers Welfare Fund. Gopal told many contractors he knew went to their homes after realizing there was no business. Nobody attended my phone last one week he said.

Hence, during the lockdown in India, Migrant workers have access to no transport, no jobs, and no food.

REVIEW-4

Pranab Mondal observed from the Express New Service at Rajasthan, with regard to migrant labourers faces a lot of challenges at the time of entry into their village due to the lockdown of COVID-19.

Migrant Workers Returning to their Homesteads in the interiors part of Jharkhand, West Bengal, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Uttarakhand, and Rajasthan, In others, neighbors have blocked the road to their homes, despite complaining to the police that they are in danger of contracting the coronavirus. The Gram Panchayats now insist on obtaining all clear identity certificates from the health authorities and must be isolated before entering the villages or residences.

Ram Sahay has been waiting at Jaipur's Sindhi Camp bus stand with his wife and children since 28th March 2020. A worker at a stone crushing factory in Beaver, he walked miles to reach Jaipur, his brothers reported he did not want to go home to Kota without screening test for weather is positive or not masses of migrant workers, who reached Dholpur Takawali village in Rajasthan, faced a boycott in their villages. Dholpur SP Myrutul Kachava told, "The villagers don't like the Migrants coming back and they are unwelcome. People grumble that workers from

Delhi, Kerala, and Jodhpur have come from toward their camps without testing, so now we are testing all.

Therefore, migrant workers are encountering the hateful act by their own village fellow people, friends, and family members.

REVIEW-5

Antony Fernando in his Observation in the Nagapattinam port fishermen's major demand is some relief packages during the period of lockdown against COVID-19.

Fishing, fisheries work, boat repair, domestic fishing and aquaculture during the lockdown are included as prohibited activities. We will need humanitarian assistance to feed our families. The government has exempted some agricultural activities. We ask for an exemption for fibreglass boat fishing and fish works together with social isolation guidelines, said RV Kumaravel, a fish laborers forum spokesperson.

Fishers also sought financial assistance like loans for hauling out repairs of modern and fibreglass boats at the same time that they stay away from the sea. They had willingly opted not to venture out to sea earlier in the month to avoid coronavirus, but the lockdown has prolonged their agony and they are fighting to feed their families.

Hence fishermen need financial assistance for their livelihood during the period of a lockdown situation.

NORTH CHENNAI'S MIGRANT LABOURER'S LOCKDOWN IS THE BEGINNING OF A CATASTROPHE

The 21-day continuous lockdown of coronavirus epidemic and the condition has drawn attention to the difficult lives of its seasoned migrants.

According to the rapid assessment Survey, 90 Percentage of North Chennai Migrant labourers have already lost one to three weeks of work. Civil society the organization that concentrates on

human rights of socially marginalized communities. This loss of income proves to be catastrophic on many fronts. More than 85 percentage of the North Chennai migrant are daily wage population, they fear food will be exhausted before the lockdown ends.

Almost every labourer fears that they will not get a job after the lockdown is over. More than 150 migrant workers in north Chennai surveyed from the lockdown period announced by the state government.

COVID-19 LOCKDOWN IMPACT ON NORTH CHENNAI MIGRANT LABOURERS

In this study one of the main reasons for food and financial insecurity is the low wages that Migrants labourers earn, More than half of daily wages and migrant's population are earning in daily wage job just Rs 500 a day, much below the prescribed minimum wage .Rs.600 and above for skilled, semi-skilled, and unskilled workers respectively in North Chennai.

Due to the highly informal and exploitative nature of the industry, workers are often paid very little for minimum wage rates recommended by local management

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF WORK:

The Analysis and presentation of work are mainly carried out the working and living conditions of the migrant labourer's in North Chennai with suitable illustration on the basis of data collected through the interview schedule.

TABLE No.1.1

1.MINIMUM INCOME STATUS OF DAILY WAGE WORKERS - RESPONDENTS IN THE STUDY

SNO	WORK FORCE CALIBER	MINMUM WAGE PER DAY	NO. OF PERSONS
1	SKILLED WORKERS	RUPEES ₹ 600 AND ABOVE	17
2	SEMI-SKILLED WORKERS	RUPEES ₹ 500 TO 600	42
3	UNSKILLED WORKERS CATEGORY -I	RUPEES ₹ 300 TO 400	35
4	UNSKILLED WORKERS CATEGORY -II	BELOW RUPEES ₹ 250	6
TOTAL			100

GRAPH:

FOOD SCARCITY DURING EXTENDED LOCKDOWN

More than 60% of the migrant labourer's surveyed have no food. A few of them said they had rations to support their homes for three to four weeks these migrants' workers have their local identity, because of that they able to get ration.

Many said they did not have enough money to support basic housing costs as a result of the lockdown being extended, this lockdown remains, how many days can Migrant labourer's households manage their expenses.

TABLE No.1.2

2.MIGRANT LABOURER'S FINANCIAL SECURITY SURVEY

SNO	MANAGE THE HOUSE HOLD EXPENSES	NO. OF PERSONS	PERCENTAGE
1	LESS THAN A WEEK	32	69
2	UP TO A MONTH	43	19
3	NO IDEA	25	12
TOTAL		100	100

GRAPH:

The Tamil Nadu government, for its part, has already increased the quantity of rice and wheat under the Corona Virus Relief Package and the economically weaker sections are already entitled to the relief package.

CONCLUSION:

This present lockdown is severely damaging the Economy, like the 1930 great depression at the global level. The income level of the bottom to top-level working classes are shrinking together. At this backdrop, the policymakers should focus the certain measures on increasing the per capita income of the country and improve the investment both domestic and foreign direct Investment specially to generate adequate employment opportunities to our abundant labourers. Apart from that to provide subsidized first-grade food grains, pulses cloth, shelter, protected drinking water facilities, compulsory education to labourers children up to higher studies. The above these are all viable strategy to improve human resource development throughout the nation. With regard to Monetary mechanism, interest-free loan to self-employed labourers . Then, the COVID-19 reflections are unexpected slip-down in the Economy even though we have taken strong, multifaceted techniques used and promulgated the such a vibrant policies to boast

the small medium and large scale enterprises for the sake of productivity of labour in the economy.

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